

SEEDLING VIGOR AND YIELD OF JAPONICA RICE SUPPLEMENTED WITH HUMIC ACID

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the effects of different humic acid levels, organic fertilizer, and half the recommended inorganic fertilizer rate on Japonica rice growth and yield. Seedling vigor, influenced by genetic and environmental factors such as nutrient availability and soil conditions, is crucial for plant establishment, stress tolerance, and overall crop productivity. Despite being a semi-aquatic species, rice is sensitive to various stresses that affect growth and yield. A field experiment was conducted in Salvacion, Alicia, Isabela, during the wet season using a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with six treatments and three replications. Seedling growth was assessed 25 days after sowing, and plant growth parameters were measured at 40 days after transplanting. Results showed no significant differences in root length at 20 days after sowing, but at 40 days after transplanting, plants treated with 5 kg ha⁻¹ humic acid had 17.73% longer roots than those receiving the standard inorganic fertilizer rate. Fresh root weight increased with 2.5 and 5 kg ha⁻¹ humic acid, while panicle length improved with 2.5–7.5 kg ha⁻¹. Although filled grain count, filled grain weight, and 1000-grain weight were not significantly affected, Treatment 4 (40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 20 bags organic fertilizer + 7.5 kg humic acid) achieved the highest yield at 3.44 t ha⁻¹, a 21.49% increase over the control. These findings suggest that integrating humic acid with organic and reduced inorganic fertilizers enhances Japonica rice yield while promoting sustainable farming.

Keywords: *Humic acid, Organic fertilizer, Inorganic fertilizer, Japonica rice, Seedling Vigor*

INTRODUCTION

Seedling vigor in rice is influenced by a combination of genetic and environmental factors, including seed quality, nutrient availability, soil conditions, and climatic variables such as temperature and moisture. It is a crucial agronomic trait that determines field performance, crop establishment, and ultimately, yield (He et al., 2008). While rice is classified as a semi-aquatic plant, its sensitivity to environmental stresses varies depending on genotype, developmental stage, flooding duration, and floodwater conditions (Mackill et al., 2012). These stressors can lead to nutrient deficiencies, excessive elongation of basal internodes, and weakened stalk walls, making plants more susceptible to lodging and yield reduction (Nguyen & Ferrero, 2006; Kaur et al., 2017; Yadav et al., 2017).

To mitigate these challenges, fertilizers and biostimulants such as humic acid have been explored as potential solutions. Fertilizers supply essential nutrients required for optimal plant growth, while humic acid enhances nutrient uptake, root vigor, and stress tolerance. It improves the physical, chemical, and biological properties of soil, contributing to better plant development and higher yields. The combination of inorganic fertilizers with humic acid is emerging as a viable approach to optimizing rice productivity while minimizing environmental impact. However, determining the most effective dosage and combination of fertilizers and humic acid remains a critical research gap that requires further study.

The increasing demand for Japonica rice, especially in Southeast Asia and Western countries, highlights the need for improved cultivation practices to enhance its yield potential. However, Japonica rice has a relatively lower yield compared to other rice varieties and is more susceptible to environmental stress. The excessive use of agrochemicals to enhance its production has led to adverse effects on soil health and sustainability. Organic fertilizers and biostimulants such as humic acid have been proposed as alternative solutions to improve soil fertility, promote microbial activity, and enhance nutrient availability. These amendments not only support plant health but also contribute to sustainable agriculture by reducing chemical dependency and fostering resilience against biotic and abiotic stresses.

Given these considerations, this study aims to evaluate the effects of different levels of inorganic and organic fertilizers combined with humic acid on the seedling vigor and yield performance of Japonica rice under direct-seeded conditions. Identifying the most effective combination will help establish optimal fertilization strategies that maximize productivity while ensuring environmental sustainability.

Research Questions

This study seeks to address the following research questions:

1. What is the effect of humic acid, inorganic fertilizers, and organic fertilizers on the growth and yield performance of Japonica rice?

2. Does the application of humic acid in combination with inorganic and organic fertilizers enhance seedling vigor and yield in Japonica rice?
3. Which levels of inorganic and organic fertilizers, in combination with humic acid, are the most effective in increasing the yield of Japonica rice?

METHODOLOGY

Securing of Seeds

The seeds of Japonica rice were procured from PhilRice in San Mateo, Isabela.

Location of the Experimental Site

An area of 291.50 square meters, previously cropped with lowland rice, located in the farmer's field in Barangay Salvacion, Alicia, Isabela, was used for the study. The area is flat, well-irrigated, and has proper drainage.

Land Preparation

Thorough land preparation is essential for successful production. The land was prepared thoroughly to ensure high seed emergence and uniform rice stand. A conventional method of preparing lowland field was employed by plowing once and harrowing two times. Lastly, harrowing will be done to finally level the field.

Testing the Viability of the Seeds and Soaking of Seeds in Humic Acid

The viability of the rice seeds was determined using the ragdoll method to assess their suitability for planting and to serve as a basis for estimating the required seed quantity for the area. The rice seeds were soaked in humic acid overnight, in addition to being incorporated with inorganic and organic fertilizers, to enhance germination percentage, root development, and survival rate.

Soil Analysis

Soil samples were analyzed before fertilizer incorporation to determine organic matter content, as well as pH, nitrogen, potassium, and phosphorus levels. A one-kilogram soil sample from the experimental area was air-dried, cleared of foreign materials, and sent to the Cagayan Valley Integrated Agricultural Laboratory for analysis. The results served as the basis for fertilizer application.

Fertilizer Application

The rate of organic fertilizer, based on the soil analysis, was applied as a basal treatment. Inorganic fertilizer was applied through split application, with half of the nitrogen and all of the phosphorus and potassium applied as basal. The remaining half of

the nitrogen was top-dressed one month after planting. Humic acid, following the prescribed rate per treatment, was applied as a foliar spray and as a seed treatment.

Seed Soaking and Incubation

The Japonica rice seeds were soaked for 24 hours and then incubated for another 24 hours, covered with gunny sacks under room temperature or shaded conditions. After incubation, the pre-germinated seeds were sown uniformly in the prepared area.

Experimental Layout

The experimental area was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications. Each block, measuring 4 meters by 26.50 meters, was further subdivided into six plots, each measuring 3 meters by 4 meters. The distance between plots was 0.5 meters, while the distance between blocks was 1 meter.

Treatments

The levels of inorganic, organic and humic acid as fertilizer treatments are as follows:

- T₁ – 80-10-60 kg NPK ha⁻¹ (Recommended Rate of Inorganic Fertilizer)
- T₂ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 2.5 kg Humic Acid
- T₃ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 5 kg Humic Acid
- T₄ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid
- T₅ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 5 kg Humic Acid
- T₆ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 10 bags Organic Fertilizer

Care of the Plants

Proper care was given to the plants throughout the growing period.

1. Irrigation

The area was irrigated with a water depth of 2 to 3 centimeters, which was gradually increased to 5 centimeters as the crop grew, from panicle initiation to the grain-filling stage. The area was drained three weeks before harvesting.

2. Weeding

Weeds were eliminated to prevent competition with the crop for essential growth factors such as light, water, nutrients, and oxygen.

3. Crop Protection

Pesticides were applied when visible signs of insect pest or disease damage appeared.

Data Gathered

Ten representative sample plants were taken within the sampling area for the following data:

1. Root Characteristics

The root characteristics of plants fertilized with different sources of fertilizer and humic acid, including root length, root weight, and Shoot-Root Ratio (SRR), were analyzed to determine the effects of fertilizer and humic acid on these parameters. Roots from a single seedling were collected, separated from the plant, and washed with tap water. The root samples were then evenly dispersed in a plastic tray with a thin layer of water and measured using a ruler. Afterward, the roots were air-dried and weighed using a digital balance.

The samples were also used to determine the root-to-shoot ratio by separating the roots from the shoots at the soil line. The weight and height of the roots and shoots for each plant were recorded and analyzed using the following formula:

Root-Shoot Ratio = Dry weight of roots/Dry weight of top of the plant

2. Plant Height

The height of ten representative sample plants was measured from the base to the tip of the tallest leaf using a meter stick at harvest.

3. Number of Tillers

The number of tillers per hill was counted from ten sample plants and averaged by dividing the total count by ten.

4. Number of Productive Tillers

The productive tillers were separated from the non-productive tillers. Afterward, they were counted and tabulated.

5. Number of Filled Grains

The number of filled and unfilled spikelets was counted from ten representative plants. Afterward, the total was divided by ten to obtain the average number of filled and unfilled spikelets per panicle.

6. Length of Panicle

The panicle length of ten representative sample plants was measured using a ruler.

7. Weight of 1,000 Seeds.

After drying to 14% moisture content, the weight of 1,000 seeds was recorded for statistical analysis.

8. Yield per Sampling Area.

The yield per sampling area was recorded and statistically tabulated, then projected to a hectare basis.

9. Computed Yield per Hectare.

The computed yield per hectare was recorded in kilograms and tons using the following formula:

$$\text{Yield per hectare} = (\text{Yield per sampling area} / \text{sampling area}) \times 10,000 \text{ m}^2$$

Harvesting, Threshing, and Drying

The plants were harvested when 80% of the grains showed signs of maturity or when the leaves turned golden yellow.

Statistical Analysis

All gathered data were tabulated and analyzed following the Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). Treatment means showing significant results from ANOVA were compared using Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test.

OBSERVATION

1. Percentage Germination

A high germination percentage of approximately 99% was recorded using the ragdoll method. Seed germination was completed 3 to 5 days after sowing.

2. General Stand and Vigor of the Crops

Adequate nutrient supply during the early stages of crop development promoted healthy germination and uniform seedling emergence. Throughout the study period, the plants exhibited a good stand.

3. Occurrence of Insect Pests

A minimal incidence of rice leaf roller (*Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*) was observed during the early stage of plant growth due to cloudy and humid weather. However, this did not reduce crop vigor, as it was immediately controlled through pesticide application.

Plastic nets were installed to prevent rats from climbing and foraging in the experimental area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Seedling Vigor

1. Root Length

Root length of the Japonica rice variety, as affected by different levels of humic acid at 20 and 40 days after sowing, was not significantly influenced by the varying doses, as shown in Table 1. At 20 days after sowing, plants exhibited mean root lengths ranging from 8.23 cm to 10.10 cm, indicating that the roots were still in the initial phases of forming primary and secondary roots with limited structural differences. The similarity in root length among Japonica rice plants may be attributed to uniform soil texture, moisture levels, and nutrient availability, which can contribute to similar root development.

At 40 days after sowing, plants fertilized with 40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 5 kg humic acid (T5) recorded a mean root length of 16.33 cm, which was 17.73% longer than the roots of plants treated with the recommended rate of inorganic fertilizer (13.87 cm). This suggests that the addition of 20 bags of vermicompost and 5 kg of humic acid likely enhanced nutrient availability and absorption, promoting better root growth compared to the standard inorganic fertilizer application (T1). However, the absence of micronutrient application in the control treatment may have led to root elongation as plants extended their roots in search of limited soil nutrients (Shahzad & Amtmann, 2017). This may explain why root elongation in the control treatment was similar to that in plots treated with organic materials and humic acid, which are rich in micronutrients.

Regarding plants supplemented with organic fertilizer and humic acid, Canellas et al. (2015) stated that humic acid enhances root architecture, particularly root size and root hair development, by stimulating H⁺-ATPase activity in the cell membrane. Additionally, vermicompost increases nutrient availability in the soil matrix, promoting enhanced root growth (Patnaik et al., 2020).

Table 1. Root Length 20 Days After Sowing and at 40 Days After Sowing (cm)

TREATMENT	MEAN	
	20 DAS	40 DAS
T ₁ – 80-10-60 kg NPK per hectare (RR)	9.43	13.87
T ₂ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 2.5 kg Humic Acid	10.10	13.40
T ₃ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 5 kg Humic Acid	8.23	15.83

T ₄ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid	8.30	13.67
T ₅ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 5 kg Humic Acid	9.43	16.33
T ₆ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer	8.56	13.10
RESULTS	ns	ns
ANOVA	10.82	9.61

ns-not significant

2. Shoot Length

The shoot length of Japonica rice is an important parameter of seedling vigor, as it indicates the overall growth potential and health of seedlings. However, the combination of organic and inorganic fertilizers with varying levels of humic acid did not significantly influence shoot length at 20 DAS and 40 DAT, as shown in Table 2.

Plants treated with the recommended rate of inorganic fertilizer (T₁) had an average shoot length of 25.66 cm, which was comparable to those treated with a constant rate of organic fertilizer and humic acid, with corresponding values of 29.50 cm (T₂), 28.83 cm (T₅), 27.23 cm (T₆), and 26.00 cm in both T₃ and T₄ (40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 20 bags organic fertilizer + 7.5 kg humic acid).

Although the differences were insignificant, a slight increase in shoot length was observed in plants treated with humic acid compared to those without it. This could be attributed to enhanced nutrient availability from organic fertilizer and humic acid, which are known to increase leaf chlorophyll content (Dahal, 2021) and promote biomass growth. Additionally, despite the improved root systems observed across all treatments, as indicated by root length measurements, no significant increase in biomass weight was recorded.

Table 2. Shoot Length 20 Days After Sowing and 40 Days After Sowing (cm)

TREATMENT	MEAN	
	20 DAS	40 DAS
T ₁ – 80-10-60 kg NPK per hectare (RR)	25.66	38.00
T ₂ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 2.5 kg Humic Acid	29.50	42.00
T ₃ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 5 kg Humic Acid	26.00	43.33
T ₄ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid	26.00	41.03
T ₅ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 5 kg Humic Acid	28.83	43.47

T ₆ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer	27.23	45.17
RESULTS	ns	ns
ANOVA	10.82	12.32

ns-not significant

3. Weight of Roots

Fresh root weight was measured at 20 and 40 days after sowing, as shown in Table 3. The results indicate that fresh belowground biomass was not significantly affected by humic acid application at 20 days after sowing. Regardless of the levels of humic acid as a micronutrient supplement, root weight remained consistent across all treatments, with mean values ranging from 38.00 grams to 43.33 grams.

However, humic acid application tended to increase the root weight of Japonica rice by 25.43% in T5 (40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 5 kg humic acid), which was comparable to the root weight observed in T3 (40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 20 bags organic fertilizer + 5 kg humic acid) at 3.00 grams. These were followed by plants without humic acid supplementation (T1 – 2.67 grams), those treated with 7.5 kg humic acid per hectare (T4), 2.5 kg humic acid (T2 – 2.63 grams), and T6 (40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 20 bags organic fertilizer – 2.53 grams). Overall, the highest root weight was recorded in T5 and T3, indicating that humic acid contributed positively to root biomass compared to other treatments.

This supports the findings of Büyükkeskin et al. (2015), who reported that humic acid at a concentration of approximately 10 mL L⁻¹ increases fresh root weight by about 24–35%, which is consistent with the results of this study. According to Büyükkeskin et al., the balance between the root and shoot systems is maintained through specific physiological activities rather than changes in the biomass distribution ratio. Greater root weight accumulation sustains root activity, ensures adequate nutrient and water uptake for the shoot, and enhances photosynthate accumulation in the shoot, as cited by Engels (1994).

Table 3. Weight of Roots at 20 After Sowing and 40 Days After Sowing (g)

TREATMENT	MEAN	
	20 DAS	40 DAS
T ₁ – 80-10-60 kg NPK per hectare (RR)	38.00	2.67 b
T ₂ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 2.5 kg Humic Acid	42.00	2.63 b
T ₃ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 5 kg Humic Acid	43.33	3.00 ab

T ₄ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid	41.03	2.67 b
T ₅ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 5 kg Humic Acid	43.47	3.60 a
T ₆ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer	45.17	2.53 b
RESULTS	ns	*
ANOVA	12.32	8.33

Note: Means with the same letter are not significantly different using HSD.
ns-not significant

4. Shoot-Root Ratio

The levels of humic acid in combination with vermicompost significantly influenced the shoot-root ratio of Japonica rice, as shown in Table 4. Among the treated plants, T₅ (40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 5 kg humic acid), T₁ (80-10-60 kg NPK ha⁻¹, recommended rate), and T₃ (40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 20 bags organic fertilizer + 5 kg humic acid) recorded the highest shoot-root ratios of 0.17 and 0.16, respectively. These treatments produced the most favorable results for plant biomass. However, plants treated with 7.5 kg humic acid (T₄), 2.5 kg humic acid (T₂), and those without humic acid (T₆) had lower shoot-root ratios of 0.15, 0.14, and 0.13, respectively.

The low shoot-root ratio of 0.17 after fertilization and humic acid application suggests that the shoots were significantly longer than the roots, indicating a greater allocation of biomass to the shoots. This adaptation may enhance nutrient and water uptake under specific conditions. A higher shoot biomass is advantageous, as it increases leaf surface area for capturing sunlight, which is crucial for photosynthesis. Enhanced photosynthesis can lead to faster growth and better energy production.

Overall, the positive impact of humic acid on plant growth is attributed to its protective action against various environmental stresses, including heavy metal toxicity (Haider et al., 2021), salinity (Saidimoradi et al., 2019), drought (Qiu et al., 2020), and high temperatures (Khan et al., 2020).

Table 4. Shoot-Root Ratio of Japonica Rice

TREATMENT	MEAN
T ₁ – 80-10-60 kg NPK per hectare (RR)	0.16a
T ₂ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 2.5 kg Humic Acid	0.14ab
T ₃ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 5 kg Humic Acid	0.16a
T ₄ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid	0.15ab
T ₅ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 5 kg Humic Acid	0.17a
T ₆ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer	0.13b

RESULTS	**
ANOVA	7.18

Note: Means with the same letter are not significantly different using HSD.

B. Growth and Yield Parameters

1. Plant Height at Maturity

Plant heights increased over time and were measured at maturity; however, no significant differences were observed across treatments. The recorded heights ranged from 87.26 cm to 91.53 cm, indicating that the treatments applied did not significantly affect the final plant height, and all plants exhibited uniform growth. The height of Japonica rice may be more strongly influenced by genetic factors or other aspects of plant development, such as vegetative growth, flowering, and overall plant health, which may not be as responsive to soil amendments like humic acid and vermicompost.

These results contrast with the findings of Khattak and Dost (2016), who reported an increase in plant height following the application of humic acid. This increase was attributed to the beneficial effects of humic acid on plant growth, including improvements in the biochemical environment of the soil, such as enhanced enzymatic activity, microbial activity and populations, cation exchange capacity, and water retention. These factors ultimately promote plant growth and nutrient uptake. However, despite these benefits, Japonica rice did not exhibit a positive response in this study.

Table 5. Plant Height at Maturity (cm)

TREATMENT	MEAN
T ₁ – 80-10-60 kg NPK per hectare (RR)	90.80
T ₂ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 2.5 kg Humic Acid	91.53
T ₃ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 5 kg Humic Acid	90.33
T ₄ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid	87.93
T ₅ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 5 kg Humic Acid	88.46
T ₆ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer	87.26
RESULTS	ns
ANOVA	7.87

ns-not significant

2. Number of Tillers

The number of productive tillers did not differ significantly across the six treatments, as varying levels of humic acid yielded similar results. This indicates that increasing humic acid levels did not influence tiller production. The recorded number of tillers ranged from 18.66 to 22.06, suggesting that humic acid application does not substantially affect tiller count. However, the improved physical, chemical, and biological characteristics of the soil due to organic fertilizer and humic acid application may have

contributed to the slightly higher tiller count compared to Treatment 6 (40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer). This could suggest that the effects of humic acid and organic fertilizers may overlap, or their combined application does not significantly differ from their individual effects (Bhunja & Chakraborty, 2011).

Table 6. Number of Tillers per Plant

TREATMENT	MEAN
T ₁ – 80-10-60 kg NPK per hectare (RR)	22.06
T ₂ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 2.5 kg Humic Acid	21.73
T ₃ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 5 kg Humic Acid	22.86
T ₄ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid	21.13
T ₅ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 5 kg Humic Acid	19.73
T ₆ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer	18.66
RESULTS	ns
ANOVA	13.70

ns-not significant

3. Length of Panicle

A significant difference in panicle length was observed with varying levels of humic acid application (Table 7). The longest panicle length (24.78 cm) was recorded in treatments where humic acid was applied at 2.5 to 7.5 kg per hectare, with values ranging from 19.03 cm to 19.73 cm. In contrast, the shortest panicle length (18.60 cm) was observed in the control treatment. The absence of humic acid in Treatment 5 did not result in a significant difference compared to plants treated with humic acid. The application of organic fertilizer contributed to vegetative growth, including panicle length development in rice plants. This finding aligns with the observations of Mishra and Srivastava (1988), who emphasized that organic fertilizer application significantly influences panicle length rather than it being solely determined by the plant's genetic makeup.

Table 7. Length of Panicle (cm)

TREATMENT	MEAN
T ₁ – 80-10-60 kg NPK per hectare (RR)	18.60b
T ₂ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 2.5 kg Humic Acid	19.16a
T ₃ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 5 kg Humic Acid	19.73a
T ₄ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid	19.50a
T ₅ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 5 kg Humic Acid	19.06a
T ₆ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer	19.03a
RESULTS	**

Note: Means with the same letter are not significantly different using HSD.

4. Number of Filled Grains per Hill

The number of filled grains per plant was not significantly affected by the levels of humic acid (Table 8). There were no significant differences in the number of filled grains between treatments with humic acid and those without. According to Kumar and Singh (2017), the application of NPK fertilizer, regardless of its source, stimulates grain production. However, in this study, no significant variation in the number of filled grains was observed across all treatments.

Table 8. Number of Filled Grains per Hill

TREATMENT	MEAN
T ₁ – 80-10-60 kg NPK per hectare (RR)	840.33
T ₂ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 2.5 kg Humic Acid	775.66
T ₃ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 5 kg Humic Acid	712.00
T ₄ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid	828.00
T ₅ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 5 kg Humic Acid	824.66
T ₆ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer	804.00
RESULTS	ns
ANOVA	20.24

ns-not significant

5. Weight of Filled Grains

The analysis of variance indicated that different concentrations of humic acid had no significant effect on the weight of filled grains per panicle. The weight of filled grains per panicle was similar across treatments, ranging from 25.73 grams to 27.36 grams. Mean comparison results showed that the highest filled grain yield (29.10 grams) was obtained with the application of 5 kg of humic acid, while the lowest yield (27.06 grams) was recorded at higher humic acid levels. However, the differences among treatments were not statistically significant.

Table 9. Weight of Filled Grains per Panicle (g)

TREATMENT	MEAN
T ₁ – 80-10-60 kg NPK per hectare (RR)	27.06
T ₂ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 2.5 kg Humic Acid	26.73
T ₃ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 5 kg Humic Acid	25.73
T ₄ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid	26.46

T ₅ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 5 kg Humic Acid	29.10
T ₆ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer	27.36
RESULTS	ns
ANOVA	13.19

ns-not significant

6. Weight of 1000 Seeds

The weight of 1,000 rice grains was not significantly influenced by different dosages of humic acid, as shown in Table 10. The treatment combining humic acid, organic fertilizer, and 50% of the recommended dose of inorganic fertilizer resulted in 1,000-grain weights ranging from 26.03 grams to 28.50 grams.

This contrasts with the findings of Abdel-Aziz et al. (2016), who reported that applying humic acid in combination with conventional inorganic fertilizers increased the weight of 1,000 grains. However, while the use of humic acid alongside organic fertilizers enhanced growth and yield parameters, it resulted in consistent seed size across the different treatments.

Table 10. Weight of 1000 Seeds (g)

TREATMENT	MEAN
T ₁ – 80-10-60 kg NPK per hectare (RR)	26.03
T ₂ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 2.5 kg Humic Acid	27.46
T ₃ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 5 kg Humic Acid	27.06
T ₄ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid	27.30
T ₅ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 5 kg Humic Acid	28.36
T ₆ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer	28.50
RESULTS	ns
ANOVA	5.87

ns-not significant

7. Grain Yield Per Sampling Area and per Hectare

Grain productivity per sampling area and per hectare showed no significant differences among treatments (Table 11). This indicates that while humic acid may contribute to overall plant health and soil enhancement, its direct effect on the grain yield of Japonica rice was not statistically significant. However, all treatments produced comparable yields, with mean values ranging from 2,866.60 kg to 3,479.06 kg per sampling area.

When projected to a hectare basis, the highest computed yield was recorded in T4 (40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid), producing 3.44 tons per hectare. Conversely, the lowest yield was observed in T1 (80-10-60 kg NPK ha⁻¹, RR), with 3.07 tons per hectare. These results suggest that while the combination of organic fertilizer and humic acid may provide slight improvements, the grain yield remained statistically uniform across all treatments.

Table 11. Grain Yield per Sampling Area (g) and per Hectare (t)

TREATMENT	Grain Yield Per Sampling Area (g)	Per Hectare (t)
T ₁ – 80-10-60 kg NPK per hectare (RR)	2866.60	3.07
T ₂ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 2.5 kg Humic Acid	3106.10	3.33
T ₃ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 5 kg Humic Acid	3236.50	3.44
T ₄ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid	3479.06	3.73
T ₅ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 5 kg Humic Acid	2998.53	3.20
T ₆ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer	2900.56	3.09
RESULTS	ns	ns
ANOVA	14.82	14.84

ns-not significant

8. Percentage Yield Increase

The yield advantage of Japonica rice as influenced by varying levels of humic acid is presented in Table 12. Results indicated a positive yield increase across all treatments, with Treatment 4 (40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid) achieving the highest increase at 21.49%. This was followed by Treatment 3 (40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 5 kg Humic Acid) with 12.05%, Treatment 2 with 8.46%, Treatment 5 with 4.23%, and Treatment 6 (40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer) with 0.65%.

Among all treatments, the application of 7.5 kg of humic acid combined with 50% of the recommended fertilizer rate and 20 bags of organic fertilizer resulted in the highest yield advantage for Japonica rice.

Table 12. Percentage Yield Increase of Japonica Rice as Affected by Varying Levels of Humic Acid

TREATMENTS	Yield (kg)	Yield Advantage (%)
T ₁ – 80-10-60 kg NPK per hectare (RR)	3.07	-
T ₂ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 2.5 kg Humic Acid	3.33	8.46
T ₃ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 5 kg Humic Acid	3.44	12.05
T ₄ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer + 7.5 kg Humic Acid	3.73	21.49
T ₅ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 5 kg Humic Acid	3.20	4.23
T ₆ – 40-5-30 kg NPK ha ⁻¹ + 20 bags Organic Fertilizer	3.09	0.65

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the application of humic acid in combination with inorganic and organic fertilizers demonstrated a positive effect on the growth and yield performance of Japonica rice. The study found that integrating humic acid with organic fertilizers and a reduced inorganic fertilizer rate improved seedling vigor, root-shoot biomass allocation, and panicle length. Although some growth parameters, such as plant height and number of productive tillers, were not significantly influenced by humic acid application, the treatments incorporating humic acid and organic fertilizers showed notable yield improvements. Treatment 4 (40-5-30 kg NPK ha⁻¹ + 20 bags organic fertilizer + 7.5 kg humic acid) achieved the highest grain yield, indicating that the combination of humic acid with reduced inorganic fertilizer and organic fertilizer is a promising approach for optimizing Japonica rice productivity. This study highlights humic acid as a promising supplement to conventional fertilization, reducing dependence on inorganic fertilizers while sustaining high rice yields.

The combination of humic acid with half of the recommended rate of inorganic fertilizers and 20 bags of organic fertilizer improved seedling vigor, growth traits, and yield, showing potential for enhancing Japonica rice production.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, using a combination of 7.5 kilograms of humic acid, half the recommended rate of inorganic fertilizers, and 20 bags of organic fertilizer per hectare is recommended, as it has been shown to improve seedling vigor, growth traits, and the overall yield of Japonica rice. Future studies should examine long-term soil benefits, cost-effectiveness, and varietal differences to refine application strategies further.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research was conducted in accordance with ethical principles of integrity, respect, and responsibility in agricultural experimentation. No human participants were involved, and the study focused solely on Japonica rice cultivation under controlled field conditions.

To ensure scientific rigor, all data collection, analysis, and interpretation were performed objectively, avoiding bias. The research site and methodology were carefully selected to ensure validity and reproducibility. Soil and plant materials were handled responsibly, following environmental and agricultural safety guidelines.

Furthermore, the study maintains academic integrity by properly citing relevant literature and avoiding plagiarism. The findings are presented without manipulation or exaggeration, ensuring transparency in reporting results. There are no conflicts of interest, and the results are intended solely for scientific advancement in sustainable rice production.

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